

On Synthesis of Some New Organotin Compounds with Potential Pesticidal Properties. Part II.

GEETA MEHROTRA and A. N. DEY*

Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur

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A new series of organotin compounds has been prepared by diazotisation of aniline and its substituted bases. The diazo compounds so formed were subsequently coupled with stannic chloride. The 1-tri-chlorotin benzene, and its analogues, so prepared were tested for their anti-fungal and antibacterial properties by standard bioassay technique. Their relative effectiveness have been assessed. Some of the compounds appear to have large potential for practical use in agriculture against bacterial and fungal plant diseases.

IN part I (Mehrotra and Dey¹) of this series, synthesis of a number of new organotin compounds from substituted anilines has been reported. These compounds showed marked anti-fungal and anti-bacterial properties and consequently it was suggested that they can find use in practical crop protection work. In the synthesis of these compounds substituted anilines were first mercurated with the help of mercuric acetate and acetic acid and subsequently the resultant mercurio compounds were converted into the corresponding tin compound by refluxing with anhydrous stannous chloride. This was comparatively a long process, and attempts were made to synthesise these compounds by a simpler procedure involving diazotisation. Accordingly, the aniline and its substituted bases were first diazotised and the diazotised bases so formed coupled with stannic chloride to give the desired products.

In the series of organotin compounds prepared by the process of diazo reaction, the substitution is effected through the $-NH_2$ group and hence the position of $SnCl_3$ group is fixed, being the same as that of the $-NH_2$ group. This method, therefore, has an obvious advantage over the former method inasmuch as the two isomers of the resultant product (ortho and para) which are produced in the former, needing separation through partial crystallisation, do not exist when recourse is taken to diazo-reaction.

Practically all the substituted aniline bases utilised in Part I of this investigation were also used in this work involving diazotisation. However, the resulting product differed in their tin contents since the final compound had three atoms of chlorine as compared to one in the former series. The tin content of the synthesised compounds was in consequence less than that in the former. It was also of interest to study the antifungal and antibacterial properties of these compounds, with comparatively lesser quantity of tin, as compared to the former. In view

of the determinant role of tin, both as a donor of antipesticidal properties and cost factor for the final product, this synthetic procedure seems to have an edge over the mercuration process provided adequate antipesticidal properties are found in the synthesised compounds.

Experimental

Organotin compounds of this series were prepared by diazotisation of aniline and its seventeen other analogues. The diazo compound thus formed was then reacted with stannic chloride ($SnCl_4 \cdot 5H_2O$), as a result of which 1-trichlorotin-benzene and its substituted compounds were formed. The following represents the general reaction :

(R represents substituted groups as in Table 1).

The detailed procedure for the above synthesis is described below.

The synthesis was accomplished by dissolving aniline or its analogues (.05 mole) in a 1 : 3 hydrochloric acid-water mixture. This was cooled and diazotised, according to standard technique with sodium nitrite (.05 mole). The diazotised solution was trickled into a cooled stannic chloride (.05 mole) solution in 50 ml water; when on stirring for two hours coloured tin compounds were separated. They were filtered, washed with distilled water and recrystallised in ethanol, acetone or their mixture. Their composition was established through estimation of tin by adopting Lomholt and Christiansons²

* Deceased 4 September, 1972.

method. Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Shiffs³ method.

The names of the starting compound together with the final compound formed in addition to their properties and their composition have been shown in Table 1. It would appear from the table that yields of the order of 46–60% were obtained in the above synthesis. Mostly the compounds are soluble in ethanol on which account they have immense potential for use in plant protection work.

Testing for fungicidal and bactericidal properties of synthesized compounds :

All the compounds were tested for their fungicidal and bactericidal activity by standard bio-assay method⁴, using potato dextrose-agar media⁵ for fungicidal and agar solidified nutrient broth media⁶ for bactericidal properties. The method involved growing cultures of fungi or bacteria on agar solidified petri dishes separately prepared from the two suspensions. Three important fungi including *Aspergillus niger*, *Chetomium globosum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* and two bacteria covering *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* were selected for the tests. The temperature for fungi and bacteria incubation

was kept at $30^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$ and $37^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$ respectively. The inoculated dishes were treated with paper discs dipped in solution of the synthesized compounds in 1×10^{-5} mole/ml concentration. By this technique compound could simultaneously be tested against Zineb (Zinc-ethylene bis dithio carbamate) which was kept as the standard. The zone of inhibition, after one week incubation, around the paper disc was measured in mm. An intermediate concentration of 1×10^{-5} mole/ml of the compounds under test was selected on the basis of Torgesons⁷ observations in which a range of concentration from 10 to 500 microgram/ml was recommended for such tests.

Following broad inferences were derived from the above bio-assay.

(a) *Fungicidal action* : It was observed that best antifungally effective compounds against *Aspergillus niger* were those containing 4-Cl-6-CH₃, 4-OC₂H₅ and 6-NO₂ groups; whereas, 5-OCH₃ and 4-NO₂-6-OCH₃ groups showed decreased activity. The order of activity against *Chetomium globosum* was best exhibited by 4-Cl-6-CH₃, 6-NO₂ and 4-OC₂H₅ analogues of tri-chlorotin-benzene. In descending order the substituents containing 2-OC₂H₅, 5-OCH₃ and 3-NO₂-6-OCH₃ groups have decreased activity.

TABLE I. NAME AND PROPERTIES OF ORGANOTIN COMPOUNDS OF ANILINE AND ITS ANALOGUE

Sl. No.	Name of the starting compound	Name of the final compounds with their M.P. °C and yield %	Colour	Composition (%)			
				Found		Theoretical	
				Sn	Cl	Sn	Cl
1.	Aniline	1-R-benzene (175, 55.6)	Yellow	39.3	35.0	39.0	35.3
2.	6-methyl	1-R-6-methyl benzene (176, 56.5)	Dark yellow	37.3	33.7	37.0	33.4
3.	5-methyl	1-R-5-methyl benzene (180 (dec), 52.3)	Chocolate yellow	37.1	33.0	37.0	33.4
4.	6-methoxy	1-R-6-methoxy benzene (183, 58.1)	Purple	35.8	32.4	35.5	32.1
5.	5-methoxy	1-R-5-methoxy benzene (155, 58.5)	Light purple	35.9	32.6	35.5	32.1
6.	6-ethoxy	1-R-6-ethoxy benzene (210, 49.0)	Reddish	34.5	30.5	34.1	30.8
7.	4-ethoxy	1-R-4-ethoxy benzene (200, 50.2)	Dark brown	34.4	31.2	34.1	30.8
8.	6-chloro	1-R-6-chloro benzene (120, 60.1)	Light grey	35.0	42.0	35.1	42.2
9.	5-chloro	1-R-5-chloro benzene (178, 55.2)	Deep greyish	35.4	42.5	35.1	42.2
10.	6-nitro	1-R-6-nitro benzene (165, 51.3)	Deep yellow	33.7	30.3	34.0	30.7
11.	5-nitro	1-R-5-nitro benzene (171, 50.0)	Deep brown	33.7	30.5	34.0	30.7
12.	4-nitro	1-R-4-nitro benzene (100, 48.6)	Yellow	34.3	30.3	34.0	30.7
13.	3-chloro-6-methyl	1-R-3-chloro-6-methyl benzene (195, 45.5)	Grey	34.0	40.8	33.7	40.5
14.	4-chloro-6-methyl	1-R-4-chloro-6-methyl benzene (180, 53.5)	Deep grey	34.0	40.2	33.7	40.5
15.	4-methyl-6-nitro	1-R-4-methyl-6-nitro benzene (185, 54.0)	Orange	32.3	29.8	32.7	29.5
16.	3-nitro-6-methyl	1-R-3-nitro-6-methyl benzene (205(dec), 60.2)	Dark orange	32.3	29.3	32.7	29.5
17.	3-nitro-6-methoxy	1-R-3-nitro-6-methoxy benzene (190, 60.0)	Deep orange	31.0	28.6	31.3	28.2
18.	4-nitro-6-methoxy	1-R-4-nitro-6-methoxy benzene (240, 54.0)	Deep yellow	31.0	28.0	31.3	28.2

Rhizoctonia solani was best inhibited by 4-OC₂H₅, 4-Cl-6-CH₃ and 6-NO₂ substituents but stimulated with analogues of 3-NO₂-6-CH₃, 4-NO₂ and 5-Cl groups.

(b) *Bactericidal action*: The bactericidal properties of compounds against *Escherichia-coli* in comparison to Zineb, were best exhibited by 4-OC₂H₅, 6-OCH₃ and 2-OC₂H₅ substituents of trichlorotin benzene. Some stimulation with 4-CH₃-6-NO₂, 6-CH₃ and 4-NO₂ groups was also observed. Tremendous bactericidal activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* was shown by 4-Cl-6-CH₃, 6-OCH₃ and 3-Cl-OCH₃ groups; while compounds containing 6, 5-Cl and 3-NO₂-6-OCH₃ groups have shown further stimulation in this activity.

It would be evident that very effective antifungal and antibacterial compounds have been prepared which have immense potential in plant protection against fungal and bacterial diseases.

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